

Managing Security Debt across PLC phases in a VSE context

Xabier Larrucea¹, Izaskun Santamaria¹, Borja Fernandez-Gauna²

¹ *TECNALIA, Bizkaia, Spain. {xabier.larrucea;izaskun.santamaria}@tecnalia.com*

² *Universidad del País Vasco, Spain.{borja.fernandez@ehu.eus}*

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, security and safety aspects are two of the major concerns for any software system development, especially while developing safety critical systems. This is especially relevant for very small entities because they have a limited amount of resources for dealing with all these aspects at the same time. In addition, these systems are highly regulated domains and they involve a huge set of standards focused on safety and security related issues. Therefore, these small entities are not only facing hurdles related to technical aspects but also from the so called technical debt when overarching a critical development. This paper extends the assurance cases approach by integrating security aspects within the lifecycle, and it proposes a framework for managing the associated security technical debt for very small entities. A tool chain is outlined, and the approach is illustrated with an industrial use case.

KEYWORDS: ISO/IEC 29110, technical debt, safety, security, assurance case

1 Introduction

Managing a product from its conception until its decommissioning implies to manage its whole product life cycle (PLC)[1]. In fact, a product development must include a wide set of activities including *per se* product development activities and other activities such as customers and providers interactions. A PLC management requires a systematic approach throughout different phases, and groups of stakeholders among others. There are several PLC methods, and depending on the industry their terminology and activities differ. For example, the electronic design automation industry such as the case presented in [2] where they define their specific approaches for managing and developing their products along a PLC. It is widely accepted the “ISO/IEC 12207:2008, Systems and software engineering — Software life cycle processes” indicates and establishes a common framework for software life cycle processes. However, this framework does not explicitly take into considerations security and safety aspects. These two aspects are becoming critical for safety-critical domains. In fact, in the context of medical devices, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration and The National Institute of Standards and Technology have published special considerations in this sense.

For developing safety critical systems [3] assurance cases are being used for gathering product-related data such as in the aerospace domain [4]. PLC [5] is playing a key role during a certification process [6] by gathering safety requirements and product integrity [7]. Nowadays, industrial products are becoming more complex and difficult to assess due to the increase of requirements [8], and areas such as project management and risks management [9] are being considered along the PLC management as key areas. Therefore, the quality management of the products during their life cycles is still a challenge [8]. One of the most important aspects is the reduction of requirements changes [10]. Tests are considered one of the largest costs [11] because they involve time consuming activities such as test requirements [12], and we need to manage product related data throughout the entire life cycle [13]. The information flow across

the product lifecycle[14] is essential, and most of the articles in the area of PLC are related with the exchange of product-related data [15].

From a safety point of view, system engineers are widely using the IEC 61508[16]. This standard provides guidance on safety engineering using electric and electronic process control systems. The IEC 61508-3[17] specifies informative software security requirements. From security point of view, there are several standards which are relevant such as ISO/IEC 15408-1[18] which provides a basis for evaluation of security properties of information technology products and systems. The ISO/IEC 7498-2 [19] provides open systems interconnection and basic reference model for security architecture. However, none of the above standards provides an integrated approach for dealing with safety and security at the same time during the whole system life cycle.

Recently, several cybersecurity efforts have been devoted to relating safety and security from different perspectives. In this sense, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has just issued (March 2018) a special publication related to systems security engineering guidance document [20]. This document is the basis of our approach because it combines International Standards such as ISO, IEC and IEEE, and it identifies the most relevant security practices. Another relevant document is the NASA framework appeared within the NASA System Safety Handbook, Version 2.0 [21]. Here NASA describes the Risk-Informed Safety Case framework where safety cases are used for describing arguments.

Finally, the above-mentioned cybersecurity frameworks and the safety related standards are not considering or dealing with the technical debt (TD) assumed or incurred during the design of this kind of systems. Each system design requires a set of assumptions, considerations or decisions to be taken into account during its design process. Security and safety decisions are being considered at the same time, and this situation assume a debt. Once a project incurs a debt there are some interests applied to it. According to [22] there are two types of TD: the type that is incurred unintentionally, and the type that is incurred intentionally. In fact, TD is a concept to be analysed along the PLC phases because a doubt can appear at any time, and it must be propagated through these different phases. This situation is especially relevant for very small entities (VSE) which usually require guidance on how to handle these three concerns: safety, security and its associated technical debt.

This paper extends a previous assurance cases approach [23] by integrating safety and security aspects within the lifecycle, and it proposes a framework for managing security, safety and its associated security technical debt for VSEs. In fact, we describe a methodology for enabling safety and security aspects throughout PLC phases and supported by a tool chain. This methodology includes some relevant practices of the Software Process Improvement (SPI) manifesto [24]. This approach is illustrated with a VSE medical company.

This paper is structured as follows. First section provides a background on safety life cycle for VSEs, we discuss safety and security aspects, safety cases and we provide an overview about TD concept. Second section introduces our methodology approach with a tool support. Third section summarises a VSE's use case scenario. Finally, we provide a conclusion and we outline future works.

2 Background

2.1 Very Small Entities and System Life Cycle Processes

Literature reports contributions related to the ISO/IEC 29110 [25] in several industrial contexts [26–30]. Basically these contributions are related to its adoption [31], [32], but in general their contributions a wide [33]. In fact, this kind of organisations are facing several hurdles [34]

including project management and software implementation perspectives. Some of these hurdles and weaknesses are related to the software implementation, verification and validation, test cases, test procedure, software components, and software architecture and detailed design [34]. Other research works are focused on its adoption [35] or focused on SPI experiences [36–39]. In addition, there are some authors focused on tailored lifecycles for VSEs [40], and promoting the use of design patterns by these VSEs[41]. From a project management perspective, there are contributions focused on documenting management aspects in VSEs context [30]. From a technical perspective, VSEs should overcome new technologies or approaches such as microservices[42]. However, there are no experience on how to adapt the ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 “Systems and software engineering — System life cycle processes”[43] to VSEs’ requirements. This ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 defines 4 groups of processes related to the product life cycle such as agreement processes, organisational project-enabling processes, project processes and technical processes. The ISO/IEC29110 is designed to include a so-called profile for considering system life cycle processes. However, none of these standards, ISO/IEC29110 or IEO/IEC/IEEE 15288, are dealing specifically with safety and security considerations at the same time in a coherent system life-cycle approach.

In the context of safety critical systems, the IEC61508 [16] (figure 1) which consists of seven parts defining a safety lifecycle and including safety requirements such as management related, risk management, design, and integration among others. This standard has been widely used by several industries including automotive and aerospace.

Fig. 1. Overview of the IEC61508 [16]

2.2 Security and safety framework – medical devices

Recently, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has released a document (NIST SP 800-160) [44] highlighting the relevance of incorporating security and safety aspects throughout a system’s lifecycle, and therefore they specify additional security practices to be considered along system life cycle processes such as: agreement processes, organizational project enabling processes, technical management processes and technical processes. In addition, the NIST published a Framework for Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity [45] which activities are identify, protect, detect, respond and recover.

Medical devices domain is a regulatory environment with a huge set of standards and regulations. In fact, The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) published in 2016 a “Postmarket

Management of Cybersecurity in Medical Devices”[46] where they state that “the manufacturer should establish, document, and maintain throughout the medical device lifecycle an ongoing process for identifying hazards associated with the cybersecurity of a medical device“. In this sense, all manufacturers are required to be consistent with the NIST cybersecurity framework, and they need to identify the appropriate mechanisms for setting a cybersecurity risk management program. Medical devices are considered part of the critical infrastructure in several countries such as the United States [47] that are promoting the use of cybersecurity programs for managing threats. These Cybersecurity Frameworks include a set of standards, methodologies, procedures, and processes that align policy, business, and technological approaches to address cyber threats (risks).

2.3 Safety Cases

Safety Cases are widely used in safety critical domains [48] [49] [48], and they are defined as “A *structured argument, supported by a body of evidence, that provides a compelling, comprehensible and valid case that a system is safe for a given application in a given environment*” [50]. Providing a set of grounded arguments is a key part for developing safety case, and it has been use in critical domains. Basically there are two different notations: GSN (Goal Structuring Notation)[51] or CAE (Claim Arguments and Evidence) [52]. Both graphical notations facilitate the reasoning behind the arguments performed by a reviewer or assessor during an assurance case assessment.

The NASA System Safety Handbook, Version 2.0, November 2014 [21] defines a framework based on assurance cases for arguing acceptable security. As stated before, they define The Risk-Informed Safety Case (RISC) which evolves along the PLC. In fact, this framework relies on the assurance cases concept. This approach supports decision making at system life-cycle reviews and other major decision points. Basically, the use of assurance cases confers a trustworthy environment and they are used to demonstrate an acceptable security based on risk appetite. This handbook states „*system safety activities are organized around the accomplishment of clearly stated safety objectives that collectively define adequate safety for the system, and are communicated to decision makers via a risk-informed safety case that provides a compelling, comprehensible and valid argument, supported by evidence, that the system is or will be adequately safe for a given application in a given environment.*“ [21]

2.4 Technical Debt

The Debt concept applied to the software context was firstly used in an experience report during the OOPSLA conference in 1992 [53]. Martin Fowler summarized the Technical Debt (TD) concept [54] and he defined a quadrant for deciding whether an item is considered as a TD or not [55]. Technical debt is not about bad quality [56]. Instead it is a metaphor [57] which pursues to manage “inoptimalities” [58] from a structure point of view or from a behavioural point of view [59]. In fact, there are several types of contributions. Some of them are focused on the analysis of the Architectural Technical Debt (ATD)[60] and there are some proposals related to defining a framework for validation [61], and even for measuring and monitoring TD [62].

All these approaches should be adapted to VSEs needs, but, basically, we need to identify, estimate and make a decision. From a tooling perspective, there are some interesting approaches such as DebtFlag tool [63] which integrates into the development environment and provides developers with lightweight documentation tools to capture technical debt and link them to corresponding parts in the implementation. AnaConDebt [64] is a tool for tracking and assessing TD, and it introduces functionalities such as visualizing, comparing and ranking.

Finally, there are some approaches relying on Sonarqube [65] which is the base tool for our approach.

3 Research method

A case study “*focuses on studying phenomena in their context, especially when the boundary between the phenomenon and its context is unclear.*” [66]. Basically, this sentence summarises the research method carried out within this paper. Obviously, there are some discrepancies about the understanding of what constitutes a case study [67]. In this sense, we have defined a case study protocol [66] which stems from a previous assurance cases approach [23] where safety and security aspects are integrated. The problem of managing a technical debt along the PLC leads us to define a methodology and a supporting tool chain. In fact, we describe a methodology for enabling safety, security and TD aspects throughout PLC phases and supported by a tool chain. This methodology includes some relevant practices of the Software Process Improvement (SPI) manifesto [24]. This approach is illustrated with a VSE medical company. Once we have defined them, we apply them into a real scenario of a VSE. Therefore, observation with low degree of interaction is a key aspect to be analysed. However, we are still in a preliminary step.

4 Safety and Security life-cycle approach

4.1 Methodology

The proposed methodology considers assurance cases (safety cases) as enablers for gathering safety requirements, security requirements and its associated technical debt in a common place where these aspects are discussed along PLC. Therefore, we consider assurance cases (safety cases) as a cornerstone element of the PLC phases. Our methodological approach (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) is a blend approach considering the ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288, NIST cybersecurity framework and the NIST guidance[45]. In addition, we add technical debt related information to each decision point. This means there are specific milestones to be reached during each stage of the life cycle. These milestones are essentials because it forces to meet and agree upon safety, security aspects, and to explicitly represent the technical debt. On the one hand, the ISO/IEC/IEEE15288 does not include specific practices for security aspects, but it is a framework for system life cycle. On the other hand, the IEC61508 does not prescribe any specific practice for security assurance. In addition, we have linked each phase of the ISO/IEC/IEEE15288 with each phase of the IEC61508. Moreover, none of these standards are related to technical debt management. Therefore, our approach deals with these three aspects: security, safety and technical debt. In fact, we align them in a common framework which is domain agnostic and considering the IEC61508 as a generic approach for all safety lifecycle activities[68]. During the design of system, we introduce security practices within each phase, and thus, security and safety practices can coexist. These interactions are between these two worlds and are represented by milestones where both types of requirements are discussed in order to identify constraints and dependencies among others. In addition, these milestones must consider the related technical debt. Therefore, for representing a TD item we have identified the following attributes:

- Name: name of the debt identified
- Date: date on which a debt is identified

- Location: where the debt has an impact.
- Description: general description of this item.
- Estimated Principal: the cost of eliminating a TD immediately
- Interest Amount: how much more effort will be needed for solving the issue
- Probability: how likely is it that a security or safety issue will occur

A recent systematic literature review about TD [69] provides an overview of the main financial approaches. Based on these different approaches, the principal and the interests are based on estimations, and we are going to adopt this technique for assign values to these attributes.

In the safety and cybersecurity environments, NASA and NIST approaches are considering milestones such as Key Decision Points (KDP) by NASA, and check points by NIST, for representing milestones where stakeholders must take a decision. Our proposal considers not only security and safety, but also technical debt decisions.

From a VSE perspective, we need to avoid a huge number of milestones, and for each of them we proceed with safety, security and technical debt aspects. This is because VSEs cannot invest such amount of efforts for dealing with them, and we want to trace what, when and where these aspects have been tackled. At the end of system life cycle stage (e.g. Concept) we need to have fulfilled 5 internal milestones. For each stage, we include the activities stemming from NIST cybersecurity framework, and each activity is enhanced with technical debt considerations:

- Identify (ID): security requirements are considered and added to the resulting assurance case. All these security requirements can be related to safety requirements. A first trade off process between them are considered. Each relationship shall be included as a risk, and a technical debt item must be identified.
- Protect (PR): for each requirement we identify a set of protection mechanisms. From a technical debt perspective, we estimate principal and interests.
- Detect (DE): based on potential scenarios there is a detection of potential threats. We confirm the estimated probability for the TD item.
- Respond (RS): the resulting assurance case contains measures on how respond to each potential threat. This is part of the risk management process.
- Recover (RC): the assurance case should contain how to recover the system from an unforeseen event. Traditionally this aspect is not included as part of the assurance cases. We resume the TD item.

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 System Life Cycle Processes	Representative System Life Cycle stages					
	Concept	Development	Production	Utilization	Support	Retirement
Technical	IDENTIFY (ID)	IDENTIFY (ID)	IDENTIFY (ID)	IDENTIFY (ID)	IDENTIFY (ID)	IDENTIFY (ID)
	PROTECT (PR)	PROTECT (PR)	PROTECT (PR)	PROTECT (PR)	PROTECT (PR)	PROTECT (PR)
	DETECT (DE)	DETECT (DE)	DETECT (DE)	DETECT (DE)	DETECT (DE)	DETECT (DE)
	RESPOND (RS)	RESPOND (RS)	RESPOND (RS)	RESPOND (RS)	RESPOND (RS)	RESPOND (RS)
	RECOVER (RC)	RECOVER (RC)	RECOVER (RC)	RECOVER (RC)	RECOVER (RC)	RECOVER (RC)
Key Decision Points (NASA)		◆	◆	◆	◆	◆
Check Points (NIST)	Focused on identifying	Focused on identifying	Focused on identifying	Focused on identifying	Focused on identifying	Focused on identifying
Our proposal	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list	ID,PR,DE,RS,RC TD list

Fig. 2. Methodological approach for safety and security using assurance cases

Table 1 represents an excerpt of cybersecurity activities to be carried out during the system analysis process. All of them are considered as requirements in every system, so they should be considered when analyzing a system. For example, the first activity described in table 1 as “Identify the security aspects of the problem or question that requires system analysis” is an activity which requires as an evidence the identification of the problem. Assurance cases must include the scenarios and the scope for a specific component. In addition, a technical debt is integrated with the assurance cases developments. This is not the sole activity with a technical debt consideration. In fact, every activity considers the TD list which is used on each phase. For example, “Apply the selected security analysis methods to perform the security aspects of required system analysis” activity requires a tool support for analysing source code vulnerabilities, and in our case we used a tool chain.

Table 1. Security activities during the system analysis process

Prepare For The Security Aspects Of System Analysis	Identify the security aspects of the problem or question that requires system analysis
	Identify the stakeholders of the security aspects of system analysis
	Define the objectives, scope, level of fidelity, and level of assurance of the security aspects of system analysis.
	Select the methods associated with the security aspects of system analysis.
	Define the security aspects of the system analysis strategy.
	Identify, plan for, and obtain access to enabling systems or services to support the security aspects of the system analysis process.
	Collect the data and inputs needed for the security aspects of system analysis
Perform the security aspects of system analysis	Identify and validate the assumptions associated with the security aspects of system analysis
	Apply the selected security analysis methods to perform the security aspects of required system analysis
	Review the security aspects of the system analysis results for quality and validity

	Establish conclusions, recommendations, and rationale based on the results of the security aspects of system analysis.
	Record the results of the security aspects of system analysis.
Manage the security aspects of system analysis	Maintain traceability of the security aspects of the system analysis results
	Provide security-relevant system analysis information items that have been selected for baselines

Fig. 3. Assurance cases schema and how objectives are decomposed until evidence

Fig.3 introduces a decision point (“Safety Security decision point”) which is a new concept in assurance cases. This decision point represents a decision between safety and security aspects, and it includes the associated technical debt item. This TD item is added to a TD list which is used along the PLC. This decision point is used during the trade-off process between safety and security aspects, and it should be analysed and balanced. NASA and NIST include a similar concept, but their approaches do not include an exhaustive set of cybersecurity related activities, and they do not include the technical debt concept. Some cybersecurity measures are related to the analysis of source code vulnerabilities, and therefore, our approach is enhanced with a toolchain which is explained in the following section.

Table 2. Safety Security Decision Point, Key Decision Point and Checkpoints

Concept	Source	Explanation
Key Decision Point	NASA handbook version 2	The event at which the Decision Authority determines the readiness of a program/project to progress to the next phase of the life cycle (or to the next KDP).
Checkpoints	NIST	Identify any unspecified emergent behavior that occurs, regardless if that behavior is desirable or undesirable.
Safety-Security Decision Point enhanced with TD list	Our proposal	The event at which a Decision Authority identifies, protects, detects, responds and recovers safety and security events. It includes a set of TD items which are related to the assurance case.

4.2 Tool chain

Our methodology is supported with a tool chain where assurance cases are the key elements. As stated before assurance cases must include system design related arguments and the evidences supporting the arguments. In addition, we have included decisions points to be included with the assurance cases. In fact, we represent on each decision point not only safety aspects but also security and technical debt concepts. Each decision must be registered in order to trace technical decisions and their impact onto the system. Our toolchain is based on Opencert tool [48] which has been used in safety critical environments for representing assurance cases which are used, enhanced and modified along the whole PLC. Therefore, we need a supporting tool for modelling all the arguments to be described during the lifecycle. In this sense, security and safety constraints stemming from ID, PR, DE, RS, RC are taken into account, and a TD list is maintained along the PLC.

Figure 4 outlines the schema of the toolchain (on the left) and the running tools (on the right). Firstly, the Opencert tool is used for creating and maintaining the assurance cases. As result, we have a set of evidences. Secondly, we link our assurance cases tool to a source code analyzer based on Sonarqube. This tool is essential for demonstrating the evidence related to source code analysis, especially those related to security aspects.

Fig. 4. Toolchain based on Eclipse/polarsys Opencert and Sonarqube instance

5 RGB case study

This case study is based on a case study presented in [23]. The presented methodology can be used in a wide set of environments including VSEs, but it must be tailored to each case.

RGB is a VSE medical company, and it has developed a neuromuscular transmission (NMT) device for Hospital Operating Room critical care performance. This device supports anaesthesiologists in controlling muscle relaxation during an operating room intervention. RGB's current engineering methodology includes the following regulatory aspects related to safety:

- UNE-EN60601 (European Medical Devices Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993) safety norm as the main requirements during the development stage as part of the patient safety requirements.
- The development process shall consider requirements of applicable safety standards (IEC 61508, DIN EN 62304, DIN EN 60601-1/ 2)
- The ISO/IEEE 11073 health informatics - Medical / health device communication standards.

This VSE has its own PLC which is based on the following product lifecycle phases:

- **Requirements:** all requirements are identified, and safety/security/technical debt requirements are defined.
- **Modelling:** this phase includes modelling the system, including data and resources[13], [70], [71] and the assurance cases. In fact, it is relevant for managing the whole PLC, and the resulting assurance cases are the common place where safety/security requirements/technical debt elements are modelled.
- **Simulation:** some papers such as [72] which outlines a structure for a so-called Product Life Cycle Simulation System. Concerning the TD list, there is no simulation.
- **Implementation:** safety/security requirements are implemented in the resulting product.
- **Validation:** validation is an integral part of the PLC
- **Operation:** during this phase there are several security and safety aspects that can appear. All potential cases are considered within the existing assurance cases along PLC phases. Standards such as ISO/IEC/IEEE 26531[73] also includes PLC, reuse strategies, and metadata and workflows concepts. Technical debt aspects are tracked as well, because we need to update the estimates for each item within the TD list.
- **Retirement:** an impact analysis is performed when a component is removed from the architecture. We need to update the TD list accordingly.

We have carried out a mapping (table 3) among RGB’s product lifecycle phases and our approach. Table 3 summarizes the relationships between them. Due to space limitations and to constraints with the use case provider, we cannot provide the final numbers for the technical debt.

Table 3. Mapping between the industrial case and our reference framework

RGB Method ISO/IEC/IEEE15288	Concept	Development	Production	Utilization	Support	Retirement
Requirements	X					
Modelling	X	X				
Simulation	X	X	X			
Implementation			X			
Validation				X		
Operation				X	X	
Retirement						X

In addition, we have carried out a mapping (table 4) among RGB’s product lifecycle phases and the ISO/IEC 29110. Table 4 summarizes the relationships between them, and basically, we highlight which ISO/IEC 29110 tasks are related to the RGB lifecycle.

Table 4. Mapping between the ISO/IEC29110 and our reference framework

	Project Management				Software Implementation					
	PM. 1. Project Planning	PM. 2. Project Plan execution	PM.3. Project Assessment and Control	PM.4. Project Closure	SI.1. Software implementation Initiation	SI.2. Software requirements Analysis	SI.3. Software architectural and detailed design	SI. 4. Software Construction	SI. 5. Software integration and Tests	SI. 6. Product Delivery
Requirements	X				X	X				
Modelling	X	X					X			
Simulation		X					X			
Implementation		X					X	X		
Validation			X						X	
Operation			X							X
Retirement				X						X

From a PLC generic point of view, the assurance cases include all the above requirements, and they are carried through the different PLC phases (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Assurance cases carried through PLC phases

From this case study, we have extracted a set of recommendations for VSEs involved in critical developments including security, safety aspects. In addition, if they want to manage the associated technical debt they need to follow a set of recommendations along the whole life cycle:

- Assurance cases must be defined, and a supporting tool is required. NIST and NASA are including decision points within their frameworks, and we are gathering this information within the assurance cases.
- Safety requirements must be included within the assurance cases. Requirements modelling tools enable tabular viewing and editing of safety requirements and the definition of dependencies between requirements. However, we need to include them within the architecture, and therefore, the assurance cases can be used for gathering the safety and security related requirements.
- Security requirements should be modelled in tabular form with the possibility of defining dependencies. In this sense, assurance cases must include them within the diagrams, and the arguments must highlight them.
- Security requirements shall be linkable to system design artefacts. The Opencert tool provides mechanisms for linking evidences. In addition, as it is an eclipse-based tool we can set up the links with other Eclipse based tools.
- Security requirements shall be linkable to implementation components. Our current proposal links assurance cases with chunks of source code
- Risk Analysis tool is applied along the different PLC phases. Risk evaluation and assessment shall be defined and used during the whole life cycle.
- Technical debt must include the item name, item date, location, description and the main financial aspects such as principal and interests
- The aforementioned risk analysis must be linked to the technical debt approach in order to estimate principal and interests.
- Safety and security requirements shall be assessed in a combined analysis containing the most parts of the system.
- Secure code analysis principals shall be maintained.
- Propagate requirements assumptions along the whole PLC.

6 Limitations and threats to validity

This approach has a set of limitations, and it is still in its early stages. However, we have identified a set of technical debt items which were used within the case study, but they were not fully taken into account because the estimated principal, the interest amount or their probability were unclear. These elements are:

- Conformity to EN 80601-2-30:2010.
- Conformity to ISO/IEEE11073.
- The Monitor differentiates pulses of blood pressure from the pulses of response to neuromuscular stimulation with characteristics of high integrity
- The NMT stimulation current can be set from 1 to 60 mA.
- The duration of the NMT current pulse can be selected between 1ms/2ms/3ms.
- The system must have a limitation in case the response of the patient to the stimulus is too large.

This approach is subjected of construct validity, internal validity, external validity and reliability [67].

6.1 Construct validity

As stated before, we are still working on a technical debt model flexible enough to consider different industries, and situations. Our approach works for the presented case which is related to a previous industrial experience. We need to study other factors affecting the TD.

6.2 Internal validity

There is an evident bias during the analysis of a case study. RGB provided a case and we applied our methodology and the tool chain within this scenario. Technical debt depends on principals, interest and probability. These elements vary along the time, and we need a continuous monitoring of these elements. In addition, this experience must be added to our experience knowledge base with other studies.

6.3 External validity

Concerning generalisation, it is hard to generalise *per se* this scenario. Our methodology and tool chain are domain independent and probably we can apply them in other situations. However, we do not have enough experiences in order to generalise our approach. We recognize we need more experiences in this sense.

6.4 Reliability

This study is not dependent on the specific researchers.

7 Conclusion

This paper outlines a methodology for considering safety, security and technical debt aspects along the system life cycle. Starting from a well-known standard (ISO/IEC/IEEE 152888) we have enhanced it with a cybersecurity framework for considering security aspects when analysing and developing a system. This approach helps us to balance safety and security aspects, and to make explicit the arguments behind the decisions. In fact, when we are defining an argument within an assurance case, we need to consider the following activities: identify, protect, detect, respond and recover. All these activities have an impact on the identification and mitigation of safety and security risks. Therefore, we include all these activities in order to reduce or mitigate the inherent risks of every system in any conditions.

This framework introduces the decision point concept to be used within assurance cases, and safety and security aspects must be considered and registered at the same time. The actual case study is a summary of the case study where a VSE is dealing with these aspects. For us it is relevant the set of recommendations instead of showing the values from the technical debt analysis and the weaknesses identified. Our purpose is not to reveal the results, but to extract a set of recommendations from a VSE. It is worthy to note we cannot generalise these results for all VSEs. This situation is especially relevant for VSEs which does not have enough time to deal with security/safety/technical debt aspects. In the context of VSEs this framework can be

considered as an ISO/IEC29110 profile for building securely and safely critical systems, and to track the associated technical debt. Real scenarios include much more requirements and standards fulfilment. In addition, we are not explaining how to extend or apply specific standards, nor how to describe and use assurance cases, nor the final results of the technical debt. This last aspect can be considered for future publications.

A tool chain is outlined for supporting the approach, and it is based on Opencert and on Sonarqube tools. This use case is provided by the RGB medical company [23]. The aim of this VSE is to include within their product development life cycle safety and security considerations. From these concepts we can identify the related technical debt. Some of them are listed within this paper, but it is hard to describe them completely due to their complexity. This toolchain is going to be enhanced with additional tools for simulation analysis for example.

Assurance cases are proposed as a tool for gathering safety and security aspects which are considered along the PLC, but a trade-off process must be described. This paper does not include the description of this trade-off process. As a future work we will describe this process, and we will apply this approach to other domains different from the medical domain.

Acknowledgements

Authors would like to thank RGB for providing their use case.

References

- [1] Finkelstein L, Finkelstein ACW. The life cycle of engineering products — an analysis of concepts. *Eng Manag J* 1991;1:115. doi:10.1049/em:19910031.
- [2] Stallard B, Silverman M. Using electronic design automation throughout the product life cycle, *IEEE*; 2010, p. 1–5. doi:10.1109/RAMS.2010.5447999.
- [3] Larrucea X, Combelles A, Favaro J. Safety-Critical Software [Guest editors' introduction]. *IEEE Softw* 2013;30:25–7. doi:10.1109/MS.2013.55.
- [4] Rupp TM, Surth W. Product Lifecycle Management for collaborative engineering and manufacturing in the aerospace industry, *IEEE*; 2006, p. 1–8. doi:10.1109/ICE.2006.7477089.
- [5] Kumari S, Kondeti G, Pakki S, Chandrasekhar T, Balu S. Method of safety critical requirements flow in product life cycle processes, *IEEE*; 2011, p. N2-1-N2-4. doi:10.1109/ICNSURV.2011.5935349.
- [6] Linling S, Wenjin Z, Kelly T. Do safety cases have a role in aircraft certification? *Procedia Eng* 2011;17:358–68. doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2011.10.041.
- [7] Merchant S. Role of Safety and Product Integrity. *Procedia Comput Sci* 2012;8:443–51. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2012.01.084.
- [8] Nguyen DS. Total quality management in product life cycle, *IEEE*; 2014, p. 754–8. doi:10.1109/IEEM.2014.7058739.
- [9] Larrucea X, Gonzalez-Perez C, McBride T, Henderson-Sellers B. Standards-based metamodel for the management of goals, risks and evidences in critical systems development. *Comput Stand Interfaces* 2016;48:71–9. doi:10.1016/j.csi.2016.04.004.
- [10] Ebert C. Understanding the product life cycle: four key requirements engineering techniques. *IEEE Softw* 2006;23:19–25. doi:10.1109/MS.2006.88.
- [11] Sutton B. Board test and the product life cycle. Get wise to board test strategies. *IEEE Des Test Comput* 1999;16:28–33. doi:10.1109/54.785826.

- [12] Bukata E, Davis DC, Shombert L. The use of model-based test requirements throughout the product life cycle. *IEEE Aerosp Electron Syst Mag* 2000;15:39–44. doi:10.1109/62.825670.
- [13] Guojin Chen, Shaohui Su, Youping Gong, Miaofen Zhu. The product life cycle-oriented modeling method, *IEEE*; 2010, p. 373–8. doi:10.1109/IWACI.2010.5585152.
- [14] Clermont P, Kamsu-Foguem B. Experience feedback in product lifecycle management. *Comput Ind* 2018;95:1–14. doi:10.1016/j.compind.2017.11.002.
- [15] Madenas N, Tiwari A, Turner CJ, Woodward J. Information flow in supply chain management: A review across the product lifecycle. *CIRP J Manuf Sci Technol* 2014;7:335–46. doi:10.1016/j.cirpj.2014.07.002.
- [16] IEC. IEC 61508 - Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems n.d.
- [17] IEC. IEC 61508 - 3 - Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems -- Part 3: Software requirements 2011.
- [18] International Standard Organisation. ISO/IEC 15408-1:2009 Information technology -- Security techniques -- Evaluation criteria for IT security -- Part 1: Introduction and general model 2009.
- [19] International Standard Organisation. ISO 7498-2:1989 Information processing systems -- Open Systems Interconnection -- Basic Reference Model -- Part 2: Security Architecture n.d.
- [20] Ross R, McEvelley M, Oren JC. Systems security engineering: considerations for a multidisciplinary approach in the engineering of trustworthy secure systems, volume 1. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2018. doi:10.6028/NIST.SP.800-160v1.
- [21] NASA System Safety Handbook, Volume 2: System Safety Concepts, Guidelines, and Implementation Examples 2014.
- [22] McConnell S. Managing Technical Debt. n.d.
- [23] Larrucea X, Nanclares F, Santamaria I, Nolasco RR. Approach for Enabling Security Across PLC Phases: An Industrial Use Case. In: Larrucea X, Santamaria I, O'Connor RV, Messnarz R, editors. *Syst. Softw. Serv. Process Improv.*, vol. 896, Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2018, p. 354–67. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-97925-0_29.
- [24] Pries-Heje J, Johansen J. SPI MANIFESTO. SPI Manif 2010. http://www.iscn.com/Images/SPI_Manifesto_A.1.2.2010.pdf (accessed May 28, 2018).
- [25] ISO/IEC. ISO/IEC TR 29110-1. Software engineering — Lifecycle profiles for Very Small Entities (VSEs) — 2011;2011.
- [26] O'Connor RV, Sanders M. Lessons from a Pilot Implementation of ISO / IEC 29110 in a Group of Very Small Irish Companies. In: Woronowicz T, editor. *SPICE CCIS 349*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg; 2013, p. 243–246.
- [27] Mesquida A-L, Mas A. A project management improvement program according to ISO/IEC 29110 and PMBOK (R). *J Softw-Evol Process* 2014;26:846–854.
- [28] O'Connor RV, Laporte CY. Software Project Management in Very Small Entities with ISO/IEC 29110. *Syst Softw Serv Process Improv Eurospi* 2012 2012;301:330–341.
- [29] Polgar PB, Kazinci F. Report on an assessment experience based on ISO/IEC 29110. *J Softw-Evol Process* 2014;26:313–320.
- [30] Ribaud V, Saliou P. Using a Semantic Wiki for Documentation Management in Very Small Projects. *Metadata Semantic Res* 2010;108:119–130.
- [31] O'Connor RV. Early Stage Adoption of ISO / IEC 29110 Software Project Management Practices : A Case Study 2014:226–237. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13036-1_20.
- [32] Basri S, O'Connor RV. Understanding the Perception of Very Small Software Companies towards the Adoption of Process Standards. *Syst Softw Serv Process Improv* 2010;99:153–164.
- [33] Laporte CY, Munoz M, Mejia Miranda J, OConnor RV. Applying Software Engineering Standards in Very Small Entities: From Startups to Grownups. *IEEE Softw* 2018;35:99–103. doi:10.1109/MS.2017.4541041.
- [34] Larrucea X, O'Connor RV, Colomo-Palacios R, Laporte CY. Software Process Improvement in Very Small Organizations. *IEEE Softw* 2016;33:85–9. doi:10.1109/MS.2016.42.

- [35] Sanchez-Gordon M-L, O'Connor RV, Colomo-Palacios R. Evaluating VSEs Viewpoint and Sentiment Towards the ISO/IEC 29110 Standard: A Two Country Grounded Theory Study. In: Rout T, O'Connor RV, Dorling A, editors. *Softw. Process Improv. Capab. Determ.*, vol. 526, Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2015, p. 114–27. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-19860-6_10.
- [36] Korsaa M, Johansen J, Schweigert T, Vohwinkel D, Messnarz R, Nevalainen R, et al. The people aspects in modern process improvement management approaches: PEOPLE ASPECTS IN MODERN PI MANAGEMENT APPROACHES. *J Softw Evol Process* 2013;25:381–91. doi:10.1002/smr.570.
- [37] Moreno-Campos E, Sanchez-Gordón M-L, Colomo-Palacios R, de Amescua Seco A. Towards Measuring the Impact of the ISO/IEC 29110 Standard: A Systematic Review. In: Barafort B, O'Connor RV, Poth A, Messnarz R, editors. *Syst. Softw. Serv. Process Improv.*, vol. 425, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2014, p. 1–12. doi:10.1007/978-3-662-43896-1_1.
- [38] Seco A de A, Herranz E, Sánchez-Gordón M-L, Colomo-Palacios R. Towards a Gamification Framework for Software Process Improvement Initiatives: Construction and Validation. *JUCS - J Univers Comput Sci* 2016. doi:10.3217/jucs-022-12-1509.
- [39] Messnarz R, Sicilia M-A, Biro M, García-Barriocanal E, Garre-Rubio M, Siakas K, et al. Social responsibility aspects supporting the success of SPI: SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ASPECTS SUPPORTING THE SUCCESS OF SPI. *J Softw Evol Process* 2014;26:284–94. doi:10.1002/smr.1586.
- [40] Wen L, Rout T. Using Composition Trees to Validate an Entry Profile of Software Engineering Lifecycle Profiles for Very Small Entities (VSEs). *Softw Process Improv Capab Determ* 2012;290:38–50.
- [41] Sanchez-Gordon S, Sánchez-Gordón M, Yilmaz M, O'Connor RV. Integration of accessibility design patterns with the software implementation process of ISO/IEC 29110. *J Softw Evol Process* 2018:e1987. doi:10.1002/smr.1987.
- [42] Larrucea X, Santamaria I, Colomo-Palacios R, Ebert C. Microservices. *IEEE Softw* 2018;35:96–100. doi:10.1109/MS.2018.2141030.
- [43] International Standard Organisation. ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015 Systems and software engineering -- System life cycle processes n.d.
- [44] Zemrowski KM. NIST Bases Flagship Security Engineering Publication on ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015. *Computer* 2016;49:86–8. doi:10.1109/MC.2016.373.
- [45] National Institute of Standards and Technology. Framework for Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity, Version 1.1 2017. <https://csrc.nist.gov/publications/detail/white-paper/2017/12/05/cybersecurity-framework-v11/draft>.
- [46] Postmarket Management of Cybersecurity in Medical Devices - Guidance for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff 2016.
- [47] The White House, Office of the Press Secretary. Presidential Policy Directive -- Critical Infrastructure Security and Resilience 2013.
- [48] Larrucea X, Walker A, Colomo-Palacios R. Supporting the Management of Reusable Automotive Software. *IEEE Softw* 2017;34:40–7. doi:10.1109/MS.2017.68.
- [49] Larrucea X, Mergen S, Walker A. A GSN Approach to SEooC for an Automotive Hall Sensor. In: Kreiner C, O'Connor RV, Poth A, Messnarz R, editors. *Syst. Softw. Serv. Process Improv.*, vol. 633, Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2016, p. 269–80. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-44817-6_23.
- [50] Defence Standard 00-56, Ministry of Defence. Safety Management Requirements for Defence Systems, Issue 4, Part 1: Requirements. Glasgow, UK: Ministry of Defence; 2007.
- [51] Spriggs J. GSN - The Goal Structuring Notation. London: Springer London; 2012.
- [52] Adelard. Claims, Arguments and Evidence n.d. <http://www.adelard.com/asce/choosing-asce/cae.html>.
- [53] Cunningham W. The WyCashPortfolio Management System OOPSLA '92 Experience Report 1992. <http://c2.com/doc/oopsla92.html> (accessed December 5, 2018).
- [54] Fowler M. TechnicalDebt 2003. <https://martinfowler.com/bliki/TechnicalDebt.html>.

- [55] Fowler M. TechnicalDebtQuadrant 2009. <https://martinfowler.com/bliki/TechnicalDebtQuadrant.html>.
- [56] Kruchten P, Nord RL, Ozkaya I, Falessi D. Technical debt: towards a crisper definition report on the 4th international workshop on managing technical debt. *ACM SIGSOFT Softw Eng Notes* 2013;38:51. doi:10.1145/2507288.2507326.
- [57] Kruchten P, Nord RL, Ozkaya I. Technical Debt: From Metaphor to Theory and Practice. *IEEE Softw* 2012;29:18–21. doi:10.1109/MS.2012.167.
- [58] Holvitie J, Licorish SA, Leppanen V. Modelling Propagation of Technical Debt. 2016 42th Euromicro Conf. Softw. Eng. Adv. Appl. SEAA, Limassol: IEEE; 2016, p. 54–8. doi:10.1109/SEAA.2016.53.
- [59] Reimanis D, Izurieta C. Towards Assessing the Technical Debt of Undesired Software Behaviors in Design Patterns. 2016 IEEE 8th Int. Workshop Manag. Tech. Debt MTD, Raleigh, NC, USA: IEEE; 2016, p. 24–7. doi:10.1109/MTD.2016.13.
- [60] Verdecchia R, Malavolta I, Lago P. Architectural technical debt identification: the research landscape. *Proc. 2018 Int. Conf. Tech. Debt - TechDebt 18*, Gothenburg, Sweden: ACM Press; 2018, p. 11–20. doi:10.1145/3194164.3194176.
- [61] Ampatzoglou A, Michailidis A, Sarikyriakidis C, Ampatzoglou A, Chatzigeorgiou A, Avgeriou P. A framework for managing interest in technical debt: an industrial validation. *Proc. 2018 Int. Conf. Tech. Debt - TechDebt 18*, Gothenburg, Sweden: ACM Press; 2018, p. 115–24. doi:10.1145/3194164.3194175.
- [62] Seaman C, Guo Y. Measuring and Monitoring Technical Debt. *Adv. Comput.*, vol. 82, Elsevier; 2011, p. 25–46. doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-385512-1.00002-5.
- [63] Holvitie J, Leppanen V. DebtFlag: Technical debt management with a development environment integrated tool. 2013 4th Int. Workshop Manag. Tech. Debt MTD, San Francisco, CA, USA: IEEE; 2013, p. 20–7. doi:10.1109/MTD.2013.6608674.
- [64] Martini A. Anacondebt: a tool to assess and track technical debt. *Proc. 2018 Int. Conf. Tech. Debt - TechDebt 18*, Gothenburg, Sweden: ACM Press; 2018, p. 55–6. doi:10.1145/3194164.3194185.
- [65] Stochel, MG, Wawrowski, MR, Rabiej M. Value-Based Technical Debt Model and Its Application, IARIA; n.d., p. 205–12.
- [66] Wohlin C, Runeson P, Höst M, Ohlsson MC, Regnell B, Wesslén A. *Experimentation in Software Engineering*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2012.
- [67] Runeson P, Höst M. Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering. *Empir Softw Eng* 2009;14:131–64. doi:10.1007/s10664-008-9102-8.
- [68] Münch J, Armbrust O, Kowalczyk M, Soto M. *Software Process Definition and Management*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2012. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-24291-5.
- [69] Ampatzoglou A, Ampatzoglou A, Chatzigeorgiou A, Avgeriou P. The financial aspect of managing technical debt: A systematic literature review. *Inf Softw Technol* 2015;64:52–73. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2015.04.001.
- [70] Hong-Bae Jun, Kiritsis D, Xirouchakis P. Product Life-Cycle Metadata Modeling and Its Application with RDF. *IEEE Trans Knowl Data Eng* 2007;19:1680–93. doi:10.1109/TKDE.2007.190661.
- [71] Nagorny K, Colombo AW, Barata J. A survey of service-based systems-of-systems manufacturing systems related to product life-cycle support and energy efficiency, IEEE; 2014, p. 582–7. doi:10.1109/INDIN.2014.6945578.
- [72] Sakita K, Mori T. Product Life Cycle Simulation System for EcoDesigners, IEEE; 2005, p. 527–8. doi:10.1109/ECODIM.2005.1619285.
- [73] ISO/IEC/IEEE 26531:2015 (E). ISO/IEC/IEEE International Standard for Systems and software engineering -- Content management for product life-cycle, user, and service management documentation n.d.